

Series: **PHYSICS**

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Photon – physical illusion.

The third energy of the electromagnetic wave.

Annotation

A cylindrical wave is considered and it is shown that the wave has mass, has a moment of rotation around the central axis, and therefore the idea of a photon becomes redundant. It is also shown that the energy and mass of the wave exist simultaneously as a single essence.

It is shown that an electromagnetic wave has rotational energy as a third (in addition to magnetic and electric) type of energy. Its value is calculated and the reason is explained that waves of the same intensity, but of different frequencies, manifest themselves differently.

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1. Cylindrical wave

In [4] “Consider a cylindrically-symmetric wavefunction $\psi(\rho, t)$, where $\rho = (x^2 + y^2)^{1/2}$ is a standard radial cylindrical coordinate (Fitzpatrick 2008). Assuming that this function satisfies the three-dimensional wave equation, which can be rewritten

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial t^2} = v^2 \left(\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \rho^2} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \rho} \right), \quad (1)$$

it can be shown that a sinusoidal cylindrical wave of phase angle φ , wavenumber $\mathbf{k}$, and angular frequency $\omega = kv$, has the approximate wavefunction

$$\psi(\rho, t) \approx \psi_0 \rho^{-1/2} \cos(\omega t - \mathbf{k}\rho - \varphi) \quad (2)$$

in the limit $k\rho \gg 1$. Here, $\psi_0\rho^{-1/2}$ is the amplitude of the wave. The associated wavefronts (i.e., the surfaces of constant phase) are a set of concentric cylinders that propagate radially outward, from their common axis ($\rho = 0$), at the phase velocity $\omega/k = v$. See Figure 1. The wave amplitude attenuates as $\rho^{-1/2}$. Such behavior can be understood as a consequence of energy conservation, according to which the power flowing across the various $\rho = \text{const}$ surfaces must be constant. (The areas of such surfaces scale as $A \propto \rho$. Moreover, the power flowing across them is proportional to $\psi^2 A$, because the energy flux associated with a wave is generally proportional to ψ^2 , and is directed normal to the wavefronts.) The cylindrical wave specified in expression 2 is such as would be generated by a uniform line source located at $\rho = 0$. See Fig. 1."

Fig. 1.

It is strange that the author called such waves cylindrical. They should be called conical, because in them, wave fronts are a set of concentric cylinders that spread radially outward and also spread along the axis: the previously formed fronts continue to expand while the emerging cylinders begin to expand. Consequently, the described waves are not cylindrical.

However, cylindrical waves exist in nature. Look at the magnifying glass with which the boy makes a fire at noon - see fig. 2. The sunbeam that enters the magnifying glass is obviously a cylindrical wave. Cylindrical lenses are also known, the peculiarity of which is the presence of an axis in the direction of which the optical effect does not manifest itself (i.e., there is no refraction, reflection and scattering of radiation) [5]. Another example is a Fresnel lens, which creates a cylindrical wave at the output - see fig. 3 from [6].

Thus, cylindrical waves (as well as conical ones) cannot be represented by a wave function. Next, it will be proven that for the system of Maxwell's equations there is a solution that describes a cylindrical wave.

This solution preserves the constancy of the energy flow in such a wave and the shape of this wave. It is then proven that such a wave has mass and this is a property of the wave itself, and not a property of photons. In this case, the idea of a photon becomes redundant. It is also shown that the energy and mass of a wave are a single entity and in a wave there is no transformation of one into the other and back.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

2. Mathematical model

In what follows we will use the SI system. Let us consider the system of Maxwell's equations, which has the form

$$\operatorname{rot}(E) + \mu \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (a)$$

$$\operatorname{rot}(H) - \varepsilon \frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = 0, \quad (b)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(E) = 0, \quad (c)$$

$$\operatorname{div}(H) = 0, \quad (d)$$

where

E is electrical strength,

H is magnetic strength,

ε is absolute dielectric constant,

μ is absolute magnetic permeability,

In the cylindrical coordinate system r, φ, z these equations have the following form:

$$\frac{E_r}{r} + \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial \varphi} + \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial \varphi} - \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial z} = \mu \frac{dH_r}{dt}, \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial E_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial E_z}{\partial r} = \mu \frac{dH_\varphi}{dt}, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{E_\varphi}{r} + \frac{\partial E_\varphi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial E_r}{\partial \varphi} = \mu \frac{dH_z}{dt}, \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{H_r}{r} + \frac{\partial H_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial \varphi} + \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial \varphi} - \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial z} = \varepsilon \frac{dE_r}{dt}, \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\partial H_r}{\partial z} - \frac{\partial H_z}{\partial r} = \varepsilon \frac{dE_\varphi}{dt}, \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{H_\varphi}{r} + \frac{\partial H_\varphi}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{\partial H_r}{\partial \varphi} = \varepsilon \frac{dE_z}{dt}, \quad (8)$$

where E_r, E_φ, E_z are electrical strengths, H_r, H_φ, H_z are magnetic strengths. In [1] it is shown that there is a solution to this system of equations in the following form:

$$H_r = h_r(r) \cos, \quad (9)$$

$$H_\varphi = h_\varphi(r) \sin, \quad (10)$$

$$H_z = h_z(r) \sin, \quad (11)$$

$$E_r = e_r(r) \sin, \quad (12)$$

$$E_\varphi = e_\varphi(r) \cos, \quad (13)$$

$$E_z = e_z(r) \text{co}, \quad (14)$$

where

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (15)$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (16)$$

$$\chi = \omega\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}, \quad (17)$$

$$h_z(r) = 0, \quad (19)$$

$$e_z(r) = 0, \quad (20)$$

$$e_r = e_\varphi = Ar^{\alpha-1}, \quad (21)$$

$$h_\phi(r) = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r(r), \quad (22)$$

$$h_r(r) = -h_\phi(r), \quad (23)$$

where $A, \varepsilon, \mu, \alpha, \omega$ are constants. This solution differs from the well-known wave function and, unlike it, satisfies the law of conservation of energy.

3. Speed and wave of length

Phase in our case

$$\phi = \chi z + \omega t \quad (1)$$

and refers to the motion of a point at constant φ . The wavelength is equal (as usual) to the distance that a point with constant phase travels, moving with speed v , in a time interval equal to the period

$$T = \frac{2\pi}{\omega}. \quad (2)$$

In this case, quantity (48) does not change. Hence,

$$\chi\lambda + \omega T = 0. \quad (3)$$

Then we get (ignoring the sign):

$$\lambda = \frac{\omega T}{\chi}. \quad (4)$$

On the other hand, by definition

$$\lambda = vT \quad (5)$$

or, taking into account (2),

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi v}{\omega}. \quad (6)$$

From (4, 2) we find:

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{\chi}. \quad (7)$$

From (6, 7) we find:

$$\chi = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} = \frac{\omega}{v}. \quad (8)$$

Comparing (2.17) and (8) we find the speed of movement of the electromagnetic wave:

$$c = 1/\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}, \quad (9)$$

which corresponds to the known relationship.

4. Energy of wave

Energy density of transverse vibrations in this wave in the SI system

$$W = \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon H^2 + \mu E^2) \quad (1)$$

Taking into account (2.19-2.23), we find the energy density:

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \left(\epsilon \left((e_r \text{si})^2 + (e_\phi \text{co})^2 \right) + \mu \left((h_r \text{co})^2 + (h_\phi \text{si})^2 \right) \right) \quad (2)$$

or

$$W = \frac{1}{2}(\epsilon e_r^2 + \mu h_r^2) \quad (3)$$

From (3, 2.22) we find the energy density at a point of a given radius:

$$W(r) = \epsilon e_r^2 \quad (4)$$

Thus, the energy density of the electromagnetic wave is constant in time and is the same at all points of the cylinder of a given radius. Let us also find the energy density at the wave cross section:

$$\overline{W} = \iint_{r,\phi} (W(r) dr \cdot d\phi) = 2\pi\epsilon \int_r (e_r^2 r dr). \quad (5)$$

5. Flows of energy

Electromagnetic energy flux density - Poynting vector in the SI system

$$S = E \times H, \quad (1)$$

In cylindrical coordinates r, ϕ, z the electromagnetic energy flux density has three components S_r, S_ϕ, S_z directed along the radius, along the circle, along the axis, respectively. They are determined by the formula

$$S = \begin{bmatrix} S_r \\ S_\phi \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} = (E \times H) = \begin{bmatrix} E_\phi H_z - E_z H_\phi \\ E_z H_r - E_r H_z \\ E_r H_\phi - E_\phi H_r \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

The flow passing through a given section of a cylindrical wave at a given time is

$$\overline{S} = \begin{bmatrix} \overline{S_r} \\ \overline{S_\phi} \\ \overline{S_z} \end{bmatrix} = \iint_{r,\phi} \left(\begin{bmatrix} S_r \\ S_\phi \\ S_z \end{bmatrix} dr \cdot d\phi \right) \quad (3)$$

It is shown above that $H_z(r) = 0, E_z(r) = 0$. Therefore, $S_r = 0, S_\phi = 0$, i.e. the energy flow propagates only along the oz axis and is determined in accordance with (2.10-2.13) as

$$\overline{S} = \overline{S}_z = \iint_{r,\phi} \left((e_r h_\phi \text{si}^2 - e_\phi h_r \text{co}^2) dr \cdot d\phi \right) \quad (4)$$

or, taking into account (2.21-2.23),

$$\bar{S} = \bar{S}_z = \iint_{r,\varphi} \left((e_r h_\varphi \sin^2 + e_r h_\varphi \cos^2) dr \cdot d\varphi \right) \quad (5)$$

or

$$\bar{S} = \bar{S}_z = \iint_{r,\varphi} (e_r h_\varphi dr \cdot d\varphi) \quad (6)$$

From (2.22) we find:

$$e_r h_\varphi = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r^2. \quad (7)$$

From (7, 2.21) we find the energy density at a point on a given radius:

$$S(r) = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r^2. \quad (8)$$

From (6, 7, 8) we find:

$$\bar{S} = \bar{S}_z = \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \iint_{r,\varphi} (e_r^2 dr \cdot d\varphi) = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} \int_r (e_r^2 \cdot r \cdot dr) \quad (9)$$

Therefore, there is only a flow along the z-axis and this flow of electromagnetic wave energy is constant in time. This corresponds to the law of conservation of energy. The absence of radial energy flow means that the region of existence of the wave does NOT expand. This means that this solution of Maxwell's equations describes a cylindrical wave.

Considering the energy flux density as a power density, we find pressure as a force moving a wave at the speed of light (3.9):

$$d(r) = S(r)/c = S(r)\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}/c = S(r)\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon} = \varepsilon e_r^2. \quad (10)$$

We have obtained a formula coinciding with the energy density formula (4.4). Thus, the wave develops a force $d(r)$, which is obviously balanced by the vacuum friction force.

6. Mass of wave

The wave mass can be found by analogy with mechanics: with a known energy density W and wave speed C , the mass density

$$m = \frac{W}{c^2}. \quad (1)$$

But analogy is not proof. The same formula is used under the assumption that a wave is a stream of photons whose energy is equal to an energy quantum. But we must remain within the framework of classical electrodynamics.

But we will use the well-known Umov formula [3], which connects the energy density W and energy flow S with the speed v of energy movement:

$$v = \frac{S}{W}. \quad (3)$$

It is also known [2] that the pulse density

$$p = \frac{W}{v}, \quad (4)$$

and the mass density will be determined as

$$m = \frac{p}{v} = \frac{S^2}{v^2}. \quad (5)$$

From (1, 5) we find:

$$m = \frac{w^3}{S^2}. \quad (6)$$

From (4, 3.4, 4.9) we find:

$$m = \varepsilon^3 e_r^6 \left(\sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon}{\mu}} e_r^2 \right)^{-2} = \frac{\varepsilon^2 \mu}{\eta^2} e_r^2. \quad (7)$$

So, the wave has mass and this is a property of the wave itself, and not a property of the photons “carrying” the wave. The idea of a photon that instantly appears to create a wave and instantly disappears when the wave stops moving becomes redundant. The photon is a physical illusion, just like phlogiston and caloric.

From (3.4, 5) we find:

$$W/m = \frac{1}{\varepsilon \mu} \quad (8)$$

or

$$W = mc^2. \quad (9)$$

In essence, we are back to formula (1). This means that the energy and mass of a wave are a single essence: energy and mass in a wave exist simultaneously (there is no transformation of one into the other and vice versa).

7. Wave rotation

There are phenomena in which the effectiveness of an electromagnetic wave depends on frequency (photoelectric effect, photosynthesis, some chemical reactions). This means that in these phenomena, electromagnetic waves of the same intensity but different frequencies manifest themselves differently. To explain this property of electromagnetic waves, the concept of photons was proposed.

But it is possible to find an explanation for the influence of frequency while remaining within the framework of the wave theory.

In [1] it is shown that, in addition to longitudinal motion, a cylindrical wave rotates around its axis. It shows that the speed of this rotation is equal to the derivative $\frac{d\varphi}{dt}$ of the function $z(\varphi, t)$, given implicitly in the form (2.9-2.16). Consider, for example, function (2.9). We have:

$$\frac{d(H_r)}{d\varphi} = h_r \frac{d}{d\varphi} (\cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t)) = -\text{si} \cdot h_r \alpha, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d(H_r)}{dt} = h_r \frac{d}{dt} (\cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t)) = -\text{si} \cdot h_r \omega. \quad (2)$$

Then the angular speed of the wave

$$\omega_\varphi = \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{d(H_r)}{dt} / \frac{d(H_r)}{d\varphi} = \frac{\omega}{\alpha}. \quad (3)$$

It can be seen that the linear speed of rotation depends on the frequency, and the direction of rotation depends on the sign of α . This means that there is a moment of rotation in the wave around the central axis - see fig. 4 (taken from [7]). This phenomenon – “twisting of light” – was discovered experimentally and is widely known [7], but does not follow from the wave equation – the well-known solution to Maxwell’s equations. However, it naturally follows from the proposed solution.

Fig. 4.

Density of the moment of inertia of the wave relative to the central axis

$$j = mr^2, \quad (2)$$

where m is the mass density of the electromagnetic wave. Energy density of the rotational motion of the wave

$$Q = mr^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2 = \frac{W}{c^2} r^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2 \quad (3)$$

Thus, similarly to the mass m and energy W , related by equation (6.9), the wave has a moment of inertia j and energy of rotational motion Q . We will call it the rotational energy of the wave. This energy is another third component of the energy of an electromagnetic wave. It rotates at a given radius at a speed

$$v_\varphi = \omega_\varphi r = \frac{\omega r}{\alpha}. \quad (4)$$

We find the corresponding flux density using Umov's formula:

$$q = Q v_\varphi = m r^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2 \frac{\omega r}{\alpha} = m r^3 \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^3. \quad (6)$$

Full flow of rotating energy

$$P_Q = L \int_r (q \cdot dr) = L m \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^3 \int_r (r^3 \cdot dr). \quad (7)$$

It is important to note that this flow of energy depends on frequency to the third power, while the flow of electromagnetic energy does not depend on frequency at all.

We find the relationship between the electromagnetic energy of the wave and the rotational energy of the wave from (3):

$$\frac{Q}{W} = \left(\frac{r \cdot \omega}{\alpha \cdot c}\right)^2. \quad (8)$$

It can be seen that this ratio increases sharply at high frequencies. It can also be seen that it increases sharply with decreasing α . Small α corresponds to small values of electromagnetic wave energy. It is at low energies and high frequencies that the energy of an electromagnetic wave is found to exceed its calculated electromagnetic energy. It was under such conditions that it was discovered that waves of the same intensity but different frequencies manifest themselves differently. And that is why the idea of photons was proposed.

Let us write the expression for density of total energy density of wave

$$\Xi = W + Q = W \left(1 + \frac{1}{c^2} r^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2\right) \quad (9)$$

or, taking into account (6.9),

$$\Xi = W + Q = m \left(c^2 + r^2 \left(\frac{\omega}{\alpha}\right)^2\right). \quad (10)$$

8. Quantization of wave

We can consider a pulsed electromagnetic wave and decompose it into a series of monochromatic waves. Then the energy flow of a pulsed wave can be represented as the sum of a number of flows of monochromatic waves. This means that there can be a pulsed flow of energy. The minimum value of the energy flow impulse can be determined from the known value of the energy quantum. And for this does not require the existence of a photon.

Thus, the idea of a photon becomes redundant for explaining these phenomena. Therefore, the photon is a physical illusion, just like phlogiston and caloric.

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